

Activity standardization and determination of nuclear decay data of ^{212}Pb at LNE-LNHB and first measurements in the SIR at BIPM

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Lead-212
Targeted alpha therapy
Activity standardization
Half-life measurement
 γ -spectrometry
BIPM-SIR submission

ABSTRACT

Lead-212/Bismuth-212 is a promising radiopharmaceutical with high therapeutic potential for Targeted Alpha Therapy. In this paper, the activity standardization of ^{212}Pb in equilibrium with its progeny was addressed by means of several measurement techniques at LNE-LNHB using a radioactive solution of ^{212}Pb -DOTAMTATE supplied by Orano Med (France). The primary standard was established by liquid scintillation counting using the Triple-to-Double Coincidence Ratio (TDCR) method and transferred to the Vinten 671 ionization chamber. The experimental calibration coefficients were compared to Monte Carlo simulations using the Penelope and Geant4 codes. An ampoule filled with a standardized solution of ^{212}Pb was sent to the BIPM for a submission to the International Reference System (SIR). The resulting equivalent activity was compared to the value calculated from the SIRIC software. A new measurement of the half-life of ^{212}Pb using a Centronic IG11 IC is presented. New γ -photon intensities based on γ -spectrometry were also measured. The present study on the metrological traceability of the radiopharmaceutical ^{212}Pb is an important outcome in the framework of the European project EPM AlphaMet (Metrology for Emerging Targeted Alpha Therapies).

1. Introduction

In the field of nuclear medicine, Molecular Radiation Therapy is a technique aiming at delivering high-dose targeted irradiation to cancer tumors while minimizing exposure of nearby healthy tissue. In this context, Targeted Alpha Therapy (TAT) is a promising treatment based on the use of α -emitting radiopharmaceuticals, taking advantage of the high linear energy transfer of the emitted radiation and the short range in tissue ($<100\ \mu\text{m}$), yielding higher toxicity in tumor cells compared to β -emitters. To date, only $^{223}\text{RaCl}_2$ (Xofigo®) has been approved (in 2013) for the treatment of metastatic castration-resistant prostate cancer. However, clinical and preclinical studies carried out over the last two decades have shown promising therapeutic potentialities of emerging α -emitting radionuclides such as ^{211}At , $^{212}\text{Pb}/^{212}\text{Bi}$, ^{213}Bi and ^{225}Ac (Stokke et al., 2024). In this regard, the metrological traceability to national and international standards of injected activity to patients in hospitals represents an important issue for current and future clinical studies (Bergeron et al., 2022a). In order to make the emerging

α -emitting radiopharmaceuticals available for routine implementation of TAT in the near future, the ongoing European project EPM AlphaMet (Metrology for Emerging Targeted Alpha Therapies) was submitted to the Metrology support for Health call. Started in September 2023 for a total duration of three years, the AlphaMet project aims at providing metrological support for clinical and preclinical studies on α -emitting radiopharmaceuticals such as ^{211}At , $^{212}\text{Pb}/^{212}\text{Bi}$ and ^{225}Ac .

The present paper describes the activity standardization of ^{212}Pb in equilibrium with its progeny by means of several measurement techniques at LNE-LNHB: Triple-to-Double Coincidence Ratio (TDCR) method (Broda et al., 2007), $4\pi(\text{LS})\beta$ - γ coincidence technique based on liquid scintillation (LS) measurements (Campion, 1959; Bobin, 2007), α -counting using the Defined Solid Angle (DSA) technique (Pommé, 2007) and $4\pi\gamma$ measurements using a high-efficiency NaI(Tl) detector (Thiam et al., 2015). As depicted in Fig. 1, the decay of ^{212}Pb ($T_{1/2} = 10.64$ (1) h) through β^- emission leads to two alpha-emitting daughters ^{212}Bi ($T_{1/2} = 60.54$ (6) min) and ^{212}Po ($T_{1/2} = 300$ (2) 10^{-9} s) (Bé et al., 2004). For this exercise, a radioactive solution of ^{212}Pb -DOTAMTATE

This article is part of a special issue entitled: ICRM 2025 published in Applied Radiation and Isotopes.

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apradiso.2025.112124>

Received 23 June 2025; Accepted 19 August 2025

Available online 20 August 2025

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Fig. 1. Sketch of the decay chain of ^{212}Pb and its progeny to stable ^{208}Pb drawn from the Laraweb website (<http://www.lnhb.fr/Laraweb/>).

was supplied by Orano Med. It can be pointed out that a similar radioactive solution from the same provider was recently standardized at NIST (Bergeron et al., 2022b). At LNHB, the Vinten type 671 ionization chamber (IC) was calibrated based on the activity concentration provided by TDCR measurements and the experimental calibration coefficients were compared to Monte Carlo (MC) calculations performed with the Penelope and Geant4 codes (Salvat et al., 2009; Agostinelli et al., 2003). New nuclear data are also presented: a half-life measurement was carried out using a Centronic IG11 IC recently purchased at LNHB and γ -photon emission intensities were measured by γ -spectrometry. A specific ampoule filled with a standardized solution of ^{212}Pb was sent to the BIPM for measurement in the International Reference System (SIR). The resulting equivalent activity obtained with the LNHB submission was compared with the value calculated using the SIRIC software.

2. Source preparation

The ^{212}Pb exercise was carried out using a radioactive solution of ^{212}Pb supplied by Orano Med from its production site in France. The solution received at LNHB comprised ^{212}Pb with DOTAMTATE ligand, in an ammonium acetate buffer, with ascorbic acid and 5 % EtOH. As described in Bergeron et al. (2022b), the solution was first mixed with concentrated HCl (37 %), and subsequently diluted with a carrier solution in 0.1 M HCl to obtain a stock solution of ^{212}Pb with a carrier concentration of Pb equal to $1 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ ($\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$) and Bi equal to $1 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ (BiCl_3) in 1 M HCl. The solution density at 20 °C was equal to 1.016 g cm^{-3} . Three nominal activity concentration levels were prepared for ^{212}Pb primary activity measurements, for the calibration of the Vinten type 671 IC, for half-life measurements based on a Centronic IG11 IC, and for γ -emission intensities using γ -spectrometry.

- Dilution level A ($\sim 1300 \text{ kBq/g}$ on the measurement day): solid sources for γ -spectrometry were prepared with masses of about 40 mg deposited on Mylar foils.
- Dilution level B ($\sim 9 \text{ kBq/g}$ on the measurement day): LS sources for TDCR and for $4\pi(\text{LS})\beta\text{-}\gamma$ counting were prepared with aliquots of about 150 mg and 400 mg, respectively. As mentioned in Bergeron et al. (2022b), these LS sources were filled with UGAB liquid scintillation cocktail in standard polyethylene vials (10 mL) in order to avoid ^{212}Pb solution instabilities observed when using glass vials, as reported by Kossert (2017).
- Dilution level C ($\sim 40 \text{ kBq/g}$ on the measurement day): BIPM (3.6 mL flame sealed glass ampoule supplied by BIPM) and LMRI (5 mL flame

sealed glass ampoule used at LNHB) ampoules were prepared for the calibration of the Vinten type 671 and for half-life measurements; specific liquid sources in 7 mL glass vials (standard for LS counting) were filled with 1 mL of radioactive solution (weighed accurately) for $4\pi\gamma$ measurements; solid sources of about 10 mg deposited on stainless steel discs were prepared for α -measurements for the DSA method.

No radioactive γ -ray-emitting impurity was detected by γ -spectrometry.

3. Primary activity measurements

3.1. TDCR measurements

3.1.1. Description of the statistical TDCR model

The activity standardization of ^{212}Pb based on liquid scintillation counting with the TDCR method was implemented using two different detection devices: a homemade system called RCTD1 equipped with BURLE 8850 photomultipliers (PMT) connected to a MAC3 module (Bouchard and Cassette, 2000) and a commercial Hidex 300 SL device with the Metrology mode (Wanke et al., 2012). The mathematical relationship between the experimental TDCR value and the detection efficiency of double coincidences between PMTs was obtained by implementing a specific free parameter model (Broda et al., 2007) that takes into account the decay of ^{212}Pb in equilibrium with its progeny. As described in Kossert et al. (2020) for the activity standardization of ^{225}Ac , the equilibrium coefficients of each radionuclide were calculated by a recursive technique based on the Bateman equation (Bateman, 1908) using the recommended data (Bé et al., 2004, 2013) provided by the Decay Data Evaluation Project (DDEP recommended data, 2024). The equilibrium coefficients and their related uncertainties are given in Table 1. The decay of ^{212}Pb in equilibrium with its progeny is dominated by the β^- emissions of ^{212}Pb , ^{212}Bi (64.07 (7)%) and ^{208}Tl . The β -spectra were calculated using the BetaShape code (Mougeot and Bisch, 2014). LS counting from α -emissions are mainly given by the α -branches of ^{212}Bi (35.93 (7)%). In the TDCR model, the α -decay detection efficiency in both LS counters (RCTD1 and Hidex 300SL) were considered as equal to unity (Kossert et al., 2009). Because of the very short half-life of ^{212}Po ($T_{1/2} = 300 (2) 10^{-9} \text{ s}$), the related α -emission predominantly occurs during the dead-time triggered by single pulses in PMTs from β^- emissions of ^{212}Bi disintegrations. Thus, α -counting from ^{212}Po decays is only possible when no single pulse in PMTs from the β -branches of ^{212}Bi is detected. To consider this effect, the following expression, depending on the logical sum of counts in individual PMTs due to the ^{212}Bi event decay, was included in the TDCR model (Broda et al., 2023):

$$\varepsilon_{\alpha}(^{212}\text{Po}, \epsilon) = 1 - \varepsilon_{\beta}(^{212}\text{Bi}, \epsilon)$$

$$= 1 - \int_0^{E_{\max}} S(E) \left[3 \left(1 - e^{-\frac{\epsilon EQ(E)}{3}} \right) - 3 \left(1 - e^{-\frac{\epsilon RQ(E)}{3}} \right)^2 + \left(1 - e^{-\frac{\epsilon RQ(E)}{3}} \right)^3 \right] dE \quad (1)$$

Table 1

Equilibrium coefficients for ^{212}Pb in equilibrium with its progeny using DDEP recommended data.

Decay	Half-life	Transition probability	Equilibrium coefficient
$^{212}\text{Pb} \xrightarrow{\beta^-} ^{212}\text{Bi}$	10.64 (1) h	$P_{\beta} = 1$	1
$^{212}\text{Bi} \xrightarrow{\beta^-} ^{212}\text{Po}$	60.54 (6) min	$P_{\beta} = 0.6407 (7) \%$	1.10477 (17)
$^{212}\text{Bi} \xrightarrow{\alpha} ^{208}\text{Tl}$		$P_{\alpha} = 0.3593 (7) \%$	
$^{212}\text{Po} \xrightarrow{\alpha} ^{208}\text{Pb}$	300 (2) ns	$P_{\alpha} = 1$	0.7078 (8)
$^{208}\text{Tl} \xrightarrow{\beta^-} ^{208}\text{Pb}$	3.058 (6) min	$P_{\beta} = 1$	0.3988 (8)

where $S(E)$ represents the distribution of energy E released in the LS vial, $Q(E)$ the ionization quenching function and ϵ is the free parameter. Some approximations were made regarding the γ -transitions related to ^{212}Pb , ^{212}Bi , and ^{208}Tl . In the case of ^{212}Pb , three highly converted γ -transitions were included in the TDCR model: ~ 115 keV ($\sim 4.87\%$) with an internal conversion coefficient α_T equal to 6.8, ~ 238 keV ($\sim 81.6\%$) with α_T equal to 0.872 and ~ 300 keV ($\sim 4.66\%$) with α_T equal to 0.464. The daughter radionuclide ^{212}Bi mainly disintegrates by β^- emission to the ground state of ^{212}Po (55.31%). Because of the high-energy β -spectra related to ^{212}Bi decay, no γ -transition of excited levels of ^{212}Po was introduced in the TDCR model. Regarding ^{208}Tl decay, only the γ -transition related to the excited level of ^{208}Pb at 2614.5 keV was considered due to the high-energy β -spectra of ^{208}Tl .

3.1.2. LS measurements with the RCTD1 system

Six LS sources in standard plastic vials filled with 10 mL of UGAB cocktail were measured with the RCTD1 detection system using a minimum extendable dead-time of 50 μs and a coincidence resolving time of 40 ns in the MAC3 module. The counting rate was approximately equal to 3000 s^{-1} . Activities were assessed from the mean of the results obtained with three kB values (90 $\mu\text{m}/\text{MeV}$, 100 $\mu\text{m}/\text{MeV}$, 110 $\mu\text{m}/\text{MeV}$). The maximum experimental TDCR value amounts to 0.989 yielding a detection efficiency of double coincidences of about 2.475 calculated with the TDCR model using a kB value equal to 100 $\mu\text{m}/\text{MeV}$. It can be pointed out that the detection efficiency obtained at LNHB is very similar to the value reported by NIST (Bergeron et al., 2022b). Detection efficiencies associated with β^- decay can be drawn from TDCR computation: the values are greater than 0.995 for ^{212}Bi and ^{208}Tl and greater than 0.975 for ^{212}Pb . The calculation was also performed without considering the γ -transitions mentioned in section 3.1.1 in the TDCR model. This change yields a limited variation, lower than 0.05% on the activity result. Additional measurements with one of the LS vials were also carried out using gray filters in order to decrease the detection efficiency, leading to experimental TDCR values between 0.976 and 0.99. As shown in the plot displayed in Fig. 2, no trend was observed in the calculated activity concentration against TDCR values. An activity concentration corresponding to the dilution level C (using the dilution factor relative to dilution B) at the reference date (August 23, 2024, 12 h UTC) was obtained with a relative combined standard uncertainty equal

to 0.31%. The associated uncertainty budget is given in Table 2.

3.1.3. LS measurements with the Hidex 300 SL system

A Hidex 300 SL (Super Low Level) including the Metrology mode was purchased by LNHB in 2023. The metrological performances of this commercial TDCR system were first investigated by Wanke et al. (2012). It can be noted that the Hidex 300 SL was recently applied for the primary activity standardization of the emerging α -emitting radiopharmaceutical ^{225}Ac in equilibrium with its progeny at NRC (Galea and Moore, 2024). The Hidex 300 SL counter consists in a compact optical chamber equipped with three ET9102 PMTs with frosted faces (38-mm diameter) surrounded by a lead shielding with an inner layer of copper. The counting unit is based on the live time technique and non-extendable dead-time (40 μs in the Metrology mode) using a reference oscillator with a compensation circuit, which can be fine-tuned via a potentiometer (Wanke et al., 2012). The linearity of the correction for counting losses was optimized by refining the dead-time compensation setting with α -counting using LS sources of ^{241}Am (UGAB cocktail) with increasing known activities up to 4000 Bq. The modification of the dead-time compensation was checked subsequently with activity measurements of ^{63}Ni (β^- decay with maximum β -energy of ~ 67 keV) using glass vials filled with 10 mL of UG cocktail. The coincidence resolving time was set to 40 ns. The counting rates ranged

Table 2

Uncertainty budget associated to the activity concentration of ^{212}Pb with its progeny assessed by TDCR counting with the RCTD1 system.

Uncertainty component	Comments	$u/\%$
Statistics	Standard deviation between the measurements of 6 LS vials	0.1
Weighing	Pycnometer technique	0.1
Background		0.05
Dead-time	Live time technique using MAC3 module	0.02
Decay data	DDEP recommended data	0.12
Decay correction	$T_{1/2} = 10.64(1)$ h	0.05
TDCR model	Conservative value	0.22
Dilution		0.1
Relative combined standard uncertainty		0.31

Fig. 2. Variation of the detection efficiency of the RCTD1 LS counter using gray filters. No trend is observed on the calculated activity concentration against TDCR values. The red dashed line represents the mean value and the green dash-dotted lines indicate the standard deviation.

between 1500 s^{-1} and 2200 s^{-1} and the maximum TDCR values were equal to about 0.829. After application of the TDCR model, the resulting detection efficiency of double coincidences was about 0.813 for a kB value equal to $100 \mu\text{m}/\text{MeV}$ (4.6 % higher than for the RCTD1 system). The same LS sources were also measured with the RCTD1 system equipped with a MAC3 module. The difference between both TDCR counters on the activity assessment of ^{63}Ni was lower than 0.1 %.

The LS sources of ^{212}Pb assessed with the RCTD1 system were also measured with the Hidex 300 SL apparatus using a coincidence resolving time of 40 ns. The counting rates were approximately equal to 2000 s^{-1} . The maximum experimental TDCR value was about 0.992, leading to a calculated detection efficiency of double coincidences of about 2.48 calculated with a kB value equal to $100 \mu\text{m}/\text{MeV}$. An activity concentration corresponding to the dilution level C (using the dilution factor relative to dilution B) at the reference date was obtained with a relative combined standard uncertainty equal to 0.305 %. The associated uncertainty budget is given in Table 3. The activity concentration ratio between the two TDCR systems $A_{\text{Hidex}}/A_{\text{RCTD1}}$ is equal to 1.0002 (12) meaning that both results are in good agreement.

3.2. $4\pi(\text{LS})\beta\text{-}\gamma$ measurements

The $4\pi\beta\text{-}\gamma$ method was implemented by means of a live-timed anticoincidence counting system (Baerg et al., 1976) developed at LNHb with homemade modules based on the live-time technique combined to extending dead-times (Bouchard, 2000, 2002). For the activity standardization of ^{212}Pb in equilibrium with its progeny, the $4\pi(\text{LS})\beta\text{-}\gamma$ counting technique was applied using a detection system equipped with a complete three-PMTs (Photonis XP 2020Q) set-up designed for TDCR counting in the β -channel and a classical $3'' \times 3''$ NaI(Tl) scintillator detector in the γ -channel. More details about the live-timed anticoincidence system at LNHb and the associated counting are available in a previous work (Bobin et al., 2023). The coincidence resolving time in the LS β -channel was set to 60 ns.

The efficiency-extrapolation technique (Baerg, 1973) was performed by PMT defocusing and by using gray filters on two LS sources. The analysis of coincidence counting was carried out based on a γ -window centered on the energy peak at 238.6 keV, corresponding to the most intense γ -photon emission from ^{212}Pb decay. Because the β -emissions related to ^{212}Pb decay have lower maximum β -energies compared to ^{212}Bi and ^{208}Tl β -decays, this setting provides the largest range of

$\frac{(1 - N_c/N_\gamma)}{N_c/N_\gamma}$ values comprised between 0.03 and 0.012 (N_c and N_γ correspond to the coincidence- and γ -counting rates, respectively). The efficiency-extrapolation fit (see Fig. 3) was implemented using the

classical straight line equation depending on the variable $\frac{(1 - N_c/N_\gamma)}{N_c/N_\gamma}$. The extrapolation slope was applied to the counting obtained from each

Table 3

Uncertainty budget associated to the activity concentration of ^{212}Pb with its progeny assessed by TDCR counting with the commercial Hidex 300SL system.

Uncertainty component	Comments	$u/\%$
Statistics	Standard deviation between the measurements of 6 LS vials	0.07
Weighing	Pycnometer technique	0.1
Background		0.02
Dead-time	Hidex dead-time	0.05
Decay data	DDEP recommended data	0.12
Decay correction	$T_{1/2} = 10.64(1) \text{ h}$	0.05
TDCR model	Conservative value	0.22
Dilution		0.1
Relative combined standard uncertainty		0.305

source. The resulting mean value was divided by 2.5036 (8) $\text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{Bq}^{-1}$ corresponding to the total counting rate related to ^{212}Pb activity due to its progeny (^{212}Bi , ^{208}Tl) and their respective equilibrium coefficients (see Table 1). In order to assess the uncertainty component related to the extrapolation technique, a larger γ -window comprising γ -photon energies ranged between 238 keV and 2614 keV was applied in order to consider γ -transitions following the decays of ^{212}Pb , ^{212}Bi and ^{208}Tl . This larger γ -window setting results in an activity concentration 0.17 % lower. Finally, an activity concentration corresponding to the dilution level C (using the dilution factor relative to dilution B) at the reference date was obtained with a relative combined standard uncertainty equal to 0.35 %. The associated uncertainty budget is given in Table 4. The activity concentration ratio with the RCTD1 value $A_{4\pi\beta\gamma}/A_{\text{RCTD1}}$ is equal to 1.0006 (47) indicating that both results are in good agreement.

3.3. $4\pi\gamma$ activity measurements

The activity standardization of ^{212}Pb in equilibrium with its progeny was also determined by the $4\pi\gamma$ method (Thiam et al., 2015) using a large NaI(Tl) scintillation detector in quasi 4π -geometry ($\varnothing = 152 \text{ mm}$ and height = 127 mm) with a coaxial re-entrant well ($\varnothing = 21 \text{ mm}$ and height = 47.5 mm). The detection device is coupled to a 9791 type EMI photomultiplier connected to an impedance matching preamplifier. In order to reduce the background counting, the entire assembly is placed in a 15-cm-thick lead shielding. An inner layer made of copper (1-cm thickness) is added to attenuate X-ray photons emitted from the lead shielding. With this set-up, the background counting rate is lowered to less than 20 s^{-1} . The signal delivered by the preamplifier is amplified before feeding a MTR2 discrimination module designed for the processing of counting losses using the live time technique and extendable dead-time (Bouchard, 2000). An ADC module connected to the MTR2 module for the amplitude analysis authorization is included in the electronic chain for histogramming acquisition to implement the zero-energy extrapolation.

Regarding the activity standardization, the detection efficiencies were calculated for ^{212}Pb and each of its progeny for which the detector is sensitive (i.e. ^{212}Bi and ^{208}Tl) using the Geant4 MC code (Agostinelli et al., 2003). The geometry modelling includes the detection system inside the shielding with a 7 mL glass vial (filled with 1 mL of radioactive solution) inside the detector well. The PenNuc module (García-Toraño et al., 2019) was applied to simulate the decay schemes of each radionuclide based on DDEP recommended data. The calculated detection

Fig. 3. Efficiency-extrapolation curve in the case of $4\pi(\text{LS})\beta\text{-}\gamma$ anticoincidence counting of ^{212}Pb and its progeny for a γ -window centered on the 238.6-keV energy peak. Each value on the plot is obtained from the mean of 6 cycles of counting. The uncertainty bars are determined by calculating the standard deviation.

Table 4
Uncertainty budget associated to the activity concentration of ^{212}Pb with its progeny assessed by $4\pi(\text{LS})\beta-\gamma$ anticoincidence counting.

Uncertainty component	Comments	$u/\%$
Statistics	Standard deviation calculated from the measurement of 5 LS vials	0.05
Weighing	Pycnometer technique	0.1
Background		0.13
Dead-time	Live time technique using MTR2 module	0.02
Decay data	DDEP recommended data	0.1
Decay correction	$T_{1/2} = 10.64(1)$ h	0.13
Extrapolation technique	PMT defocusing and gray filters	0.24
Dilution		0.1
Relative combined standard uncertainty		0.35

efficiencies obtained for each radionuclide of interest were equal to 0.763 for ^{212}Pb , 0.133 for ^{212}Bi , and 0.956 for ^{208}Tl . The total detection efficiency of ^{212}Pb in equilibrium with its progeny was calculated using the equilibrium coefficients related to each radionuclide (see Table 1). The resulting value is equal to 1.291 (4). The correction for the zero-energy extrapolation was assessed to 1.006 (2) for a detection threshold of 15 keV. An activity concentration corresponding to the dilution level C at the reference date was obtained from the measurements of seven sources, with a relative combined standard uncertainty equal to 0.38 %. The associated uncertainty budget is given in Table 5. The activity concentration ratio with the RCTD1 value $A_{4\pi\gamma}/A_{\text{RCTD1}}$ is equal to 0.9955 (49) meaning that both results are consistent.

3.4. Activity measurements by α -counting with the DSA method

The α -counting system designed at LNHB for primary measurements based on the DSA method consists in a vacuum chamber equipped with a stainless steel collimator and a silicon PIPS detector (Canberra PD, 2000-40-300AM) having an active area of 2000 mm². The distance between the diaphragm in front of the detector and the radioactive source is equal to 167.51 (10) mm taking into account the source thickness and the diaphragm radius is 20.255 (2) mm. Based on these values, the geometry factor G is equal to 0.36131 (44), corresponding to the detection solid angle divided by 4π sr calculated according to the algorithm proposed by Pommé et al. (2003). The activity A was determined using the following expression:

$$A = \frac{n}{G \cdot t \cdot I_\alpha} \quad (2)$$

where n is the net counting, t is the measurement duration and I_α represents the α -emission probability. Regarding the standardization of ^{212}Pb in equilibrium with its progeny, two solid sources (S1 and S2) were measured. For both sources, the net counting was determined from

Table 5
Uncertainty budget associated to the activity concentration of ^{212}Pb with its progeny assessed by $4\pi\gamma$ counting.

Uncertainty component	Comments	$u/\%$
Statistics	Standard deviation calculated from the measurement of 7 sources	0.1
Weighing	Gravimetric weighing	0.06
Background		0.01
Dead-time	Live time technique using MTR2 module	0.01
Decay correction	$T_{1/2} = 10.64(1)$ h	0.03
Detection efficiency	Monte Carlo calculation with the Geant4 code	0.3
Zero-energy extrapolation	Conservative calculation	0.2
Relative combined standard uncertainty		0.38

the energy spectra of α -counting corresponding to ^{212}Bi and ^{212}Po and by setting a detection threshold at about 1 MeV. The results were subsequently corrected for the dead-time, for the radioactive decay and for the extrapolation to zero-energy. The calculation of I_α was performed using the α -emission probabilities of ^{212}Bi and ^{212}Po and their respective equilibrium coefficients. The activity concentration ratios with the RCTD1 value for both solid sources S1 and S2 are $A_{\text{S1}}/A_{\text{RCTD1}} = 1.0298$ (78) and $A_{\text{S2}}/A_{\text{RCTD1}} = 1.0109$ (95), respectively. The associated uncertainty budget for the activity concentration obtained with the source S1 is displayed in Table 6. The large combined uncertainty is mainly due to the low statistics of α -counting. However, the significant discrepancies between sources and the RCTD1 activity concentration will need further investigations in order to be understood.

4. Calibration of the Vinten type 671 ionization chamber

4.1. Measurements of the calibration coefficients

At LNHB, primary radioactivity standards of γ -emitting radionuclides are linked to the BIPM SIR (Ratel, 2007) by means of a Vinten type 671 IC connected to Keithley 6517 electrometer, which is also used for HV power supply (400 V). It is a copy of the Vinten 671 IC at NPL, whose design is similar to the IG42 IC constructed by Centronic (Woods et al., 1983; Amiot, 2004). Two sister ICs are also in use at NIST (Bergeron et al., 2022b) and at NRC (Townson et al., 2018). The Vinten 671 IC at LNHB is a cylindrical aluminium chamber with a 10.5 L effective volume filled with N₂ gas at a nominal pressure of about 1 MPa. It includes a coaxial re-entrant well (73-mm diameter, 374-mm height) made of aluminium (2-mm thick) with a polyvinyl liner on the top (0.5-mm thick). The central aluminium-alloy electrode is 2-mm thick and it is housed in a Bakelite support (1-mm thick). In order to reduce the background, the entire IC is surrounded by an additional homemade lead shielding having a 50-mm thick hollow cylindrical shape. The mean background current is equal to 2×10^{-14} A. The homemade source holder is composed of polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA). The distance from the bottom of the well to the center of the radioactive volume is equal to 247 mm, which corresponds to the position where the response of the IC is maximized. The calibration of the Vinten IC is generally performed with BIPM and LMRI ampoules. The LMRI type corresponds to specific LNHB ampoules having a wall thickness of 0.61 (1) mm and filled with 5 mL of radioactive solution.

The measurements were carried out with three ampoules of both types filled with the ^{212}Pb radioactive solution corresponding to the dilution level C. The calibration coefficients for the measurements of ^{212}Pb in equilibrium with its progeny were determined using the primary activity concentration obtained by the TDCR method with the RCTD1 system (A_{RCTD1}). For both types of ampoules, the activity of a ^{137}Cs reference source was measured to account for long-term instability effects. After corrections for the background and for the half-life decay, the calibration coefficients are equal to 13.570 (57) pA/MBq and 13.546 (56) pA/MBq for the BIPM and LNHB ampoules, respectively. The

Table 6
Uncertainty budget associated to the activity concentration of ^{212}Pb with its progeny assessed by α -counting using the DSA method in the case of the source S1.

Uncertainty component	$u/\%$	
Statistics and background subtraction	0.56	
Weighing (pycnometer technique)	0.1	
Extrapolation to zero-energy	0.09	
Geometrical factor G	0.12	
Backscattering	0.1	
Emission intensity I_α	0.4	
^{212}Pb decay correction ($T_{1/2} = 10.64(1)$ h)	0.03	
Reproducibility (positioning)	0.03	
Relative combined standard uncertainty		0.72

uncertainty budget is given in Table 7. The agreement between the measurements of each ampoule confirmed the homogeneity of the radioactive solution. The calibration coefficients measured at LNHB are slightly higher than the value obtained at NIST (13.27 (4) pA/MBq) for a similar Vinten IC with NIST standard 5 mL ampoule. Nevertheless, the calibration coefficients obtained at LNHB and NIST are not quite comparable due to the source-to-detector arrangement (i.e. source holders and chamber surroundings).

4.2. MC simulations with the Penelope and Geant4 codes

Two MC benchmarks are available at LNHB to simulate the mean energy deposited in the N₂-gas volume of the Vinten 671 IC using the Penelope code (version 2018) (de Vismes and Amiot, 2003; Amiot, 2004) and the Geant4 code (version 11.3.0) (Thiam et al., 2016). Both benchmarks rely on a complete modelling of the IC geometry (as described in section 4.1) including the source-to-detector arrangement (source holders, ampoule type and positioning). For both MC codes, the radioactive decays are simulated using specific additional modules relying on DDEP recommended data: PenNuc for Penelope (García-Toraño et al., 2019) and Nuclide++ for Geant4 (Thiam et al., 2020). These two modules simulate the radionuclide decay as a random sequence of transitions (β - and γ -transitions), each involving either the release of electrons or photons with prescribed energies, and X-ray and Auger-electron emissions from the atomic rearrangement (internal conversion and electron capture). The mean energy deposit in the N₂ gas volume (E_{dep} in eV) is related to the calibration coefficient (in pA/MBq) according to the expression $C = e \frac{E_{dep}}{W} \cdot 10^{18}$ where, e is the electron charge and, W the mean energy (in eV) required to produce an ion pair in N₂-gas. The W value, equal to 34.8 (2) eV for N₂ at 1 MPa, is taken from the ICRU Report 31 (1979). For the standardization of ²¹²Pb, the calibration coefficients were first calculated separately for ²¹²Pb and the progeny ²¹²Bi and ²⁰⁸Tl (for which the detector is sensitive). The calibration coefficients for ²¹²Pb in equilibrium with its progeny were subsequently determined using the equilibrium coefficients for each radionuclide ²¹²Pb, ²¹²Bi and ²⁰⁸Tl (see Table 1). In the case of the LMRI ampoule, the calculated calibrated coefficients were 13.59 (12) pA/MBq with Penelope and 13.63 (12) pA/MBq with Geant4. For the BIPM ampoule, the results were slightly higher: 13.62 (12) pA/MBq with Penelope and 13.65 (12) pA/MBq with Geant4. The uncertainties associated with MC calculated values are conservative. As shown in Table 8, the MC simulated calibration coefficients are in good agreement with the experimental values, considering their respective uncertainties. Regarding individual results for each radionuclide, it is noteworthy that the calibration coefficient for ²¹²Pb in equilibrium with its progeny is predominantly due to the contribution of ²⁰⁸Tl decay (about 80 %) while the ²¹²Pb and ²¹²Bi decays are almost equivalent (12 % and 8 %, respectively). The same findings are reported in Bergeron et al. (2022b).

Table 7

Uncertainty budget associated to the calibration coefficients of the Vinten type 671 IC at LNHB.

Uncertainty component	$u/\%$
Variability of ampoule measurements and background correction	0.27
Reproducibility (positioning)	0.07
Stability check (¹³⁷ Cs)	0.01
Weighing	0.02
²¹² Pb decay correction ($T_{1/2} = 10.64(1)$ h)	0.03
Calibration (TDCR measurements)	0.31
Relative combined standard uncertainty	0.42

Table 8

Comparison between experimental and calculated calibration coefficients of the Vinten type 671 IC based on the Penelope and Geant4 MC codes.

Ampoule type	Experimental (pA/MBq)	Penelope (pA/MBq)	Geant4 (pA/MBq)
BIPM	13.570 (57)	13.62 (12)	13.65 (12)
LMRI	13.546 (56)	13.59 (12)	13.63 (12)

5. Nuclear data measurements

5.1. Half-life measurement with a Centronic IG11 IC

The ²¹²Pb half-life measurements were performed using a well-type Centronic IG11 IC (filled with Ar gas at a pressure of 2 MPa) including a coaxial re-entrant well (25.45-mm diameter and 322-mm height). In order to reduce the background, the chamber is installed in a lead shielding (50-mm thick hollow-cylindrical shape). The detector is connected to a Keithley 6517B electrometer and it operates at a negative DC voltage of -650 V. The current measurements were carried out using a LMRI ampoule (filled with 5 mL of radioactive solution corresponding to the dilution C) placed in a custom-made source holder (PMMA, 1-mm thick). The ampoule is positioned at a height of 6 cm from the bottom of the IC well. The acquisition was performed from a single insertion of the ampoule in the IG11 IC by recording 2500 cycles of 200 current measurements over a period of 24 s. The total duration for all cycles represents approximately a ²¹²Pb decay over 10 half-lives. The current measurements ranged between -13.6 pA and -7×10^{-2} pA (this latter value is close to the background level).

The analysis was implemented by applying a weighted least squares (WLS) fitting on 2500 data points each corresponding to the mean of a cycle of 200 current measurements (the weight is obtained from the standard deviation of the mean). The basic decay function was used for the fitting function that depends on the half-life $T_{1/2}$ and the background level B_k .

$$C(t) = C_0 e^{-\frac{\ln(2)}{T_{1/2}} t} + B_k$$

The results of the WLS fitting were respectively $T_{1/2}$ equal to 10.6314 (24) h and B_k equal to $-5.23(4) \times 10^{-2}$ pA which is consistent with the experimental background level. The relative residuals are plotted in Fig. 4. The uncertainty budget is displayed in Table 9. The statistical component was expanded considering the results obtained by applying an ordinary least squares fitting or by imposing the background value. The medium-frequency component was assessed based on the method proposed by Pommé (2015) considering the 10 half-life periods of measurements. The linearity is considered as the main contributor for the low-frequency component (Pommé et al., 2018) considering the current range of the measurements (less than 20 pA). Finally, a half-life equal to 10.6314 (74) h was obtained from the decay measurements given by the Centronic IG11 IC. Similarly to recent published values (Kossert, 2017; Bergmann and Jelínek, 2022; Pibida et al., 2024), this value is slightly lower than the DDEP recommended half-life for ²¹²Pb ($T_{1/2} = 10.64(1)$ h (Bé et al., 2004)).

5.2. Measurements of photon emission intensities

The measurements of photon emission intensities were performed from three point sources using a coaxial HPGe detector (ORTEC GMX-15-PLUS-S model with a crystal volume of 93 cm³) calibrated over the energy range from 15 keV to 1836 keV. The energy resolution is equal to 0.82 keV at 122 keV and 1.82 keV at 1408 keV. The distance between the source and the detector window corresponding to the calibration position is equal to 106.9 mm, with an associated relative uncertainty of 0.1 %. Active measurement times were equal to about 940 s for a real time of 1000 s. No problem of inhomogeneity was observed on massic count

Fig. 4. Relative residuals from the fitting of the current measurements obtained with the Centronic IG11 IC for the ^{212}Pb half-life assessment.

Table 9

Uncertainty budget for the half-life measurement of ^{212}Pb with a Centronic IG11 IC.

Uncertainty component	Comments	$u/\%$
Statistics	2500 measurements	0.042
Medium-frequency	Pommé's method (2015)	0.031
Low-frequency	Linearity	0.03
Background		0.033
Relative combined standard uncertainty		0.07

rates between the three sources. The photon emission intensities I_γ for the main γ -ray energies following the decay of ^{212}Pb , ^{212}Bi and ^{208}Tl were assessed as the weighted mean of the individual results from the measurements of the three sources, by using the following expression:

$$I_\gamma = \frac{N_\gamma \cdot C_{cs}}{A \cdot t \cdot \varepsilon_\gamma} \quad (3)$$

where N_γ is the net counting in the full-energy peak obtained with the COLEGRAM software (Ménesguen and Lépy, 2021) and corrected for the radioactive decay, t is the active time, ε_γ is the detection efficiency obtained from the calibration curve and C_{cs} is the correction for the coincidence summing effects computed using the ETNA software (Piton et al., 2000). The activity A was provided by the result obtained with the RCTD1 system (for the dilution level A) corrected for the equilibrium coefficients in the case of ^{208}Tl and ^{212}Bi . The uncertainty budget is given in Table 10 for the 238.6-keV photon emission following the ^{212}Pb decay. In Table 11, three relative γ -photon intensities of ^{212}Pb are compared with recent measurements from NIST and NPL (Pibida et al., 2024) and DDEP recommended data. In the case of the 115.18 keV γ -ray emission, the result from LNHB is significantly lower than the DDEP evaluation but it is in good agreement with the value obtained at NPL. The values in Table 12 provide a comparison between the most important absolute γ -photon intensities of ^{212}Pb , ^{212}Bi and ^{208}Tl obtained at LNHB with recently published measurements from NIST and NPL (Pibida et al., 2024) and DDEP recommended data. In the case of the 238.6 keV γ -ray emission, the results from LNHB, NIST and NPL are consistent with the DDEP recommended value with lower uncertainties.

6. SIR measurement at BIPM

A BIPM ampoule filled with a standardized solution of ^{212}Pb in equilibrium with its progeny was submitted to the International

Table 10

Uncertainty budget for the measurement of the photon emission at 238.6 keV of ^{212}Pb decay by γ -spectrometry.

Uncertainty component	$u/\%$	
Peak area	0.37	
Weighing (pycnometer technique)	0.05	
Geometry	0.1	
Full energy peak detection efficiency G	0.43	
Activity (TDCR measurements)	0.31	
Coincidence summing	negligible	
Variability between sources	0.4	
^{212}Pb decay correction ($T_{1/2} = 10.64(1)$ h)	0.016	
Relative combined standard uncertainty		0.76

Table 11

Comparison of three relative γ -photon emission intensities of ^{212}Pb measured in this work with recent measurements from NIST and NPL (Pibida et al., 2024) and DDEP recommended data.

Energy	115.18 keV	238.63 keV	300.09 keV
NIST (2024)	1.375 (23)	100.00 (98)	7.42 (11)
NPL (2024)	1.3275 (87)	100.00 (38)	7.516 (39)
DDEP	1.43 (5)	100 (1)	7.3 (3)
This work	1.316 (28)	100.0 (8)	7.55 (11)

Reference System (SIR) (Ratel, 2007) for BIPM. RI(II)-K1 comparison. The SIR makes it possible for radionuclide laboratories to compare their primary standards for γ -emitting radionuclides using a highly stable re-entrant IC (filled with N_2 gas at 2-MPa pressure) through the determination of an equivalent activity. The BIPM ampoule, containing 3.67030 (60) g of ^{212}Pb radioactive solution (corresponding to the dilution level C), was measured in the SIR IC on August 23, 2024, at 11h53 and 15h30 UTC. The activity concentration of the solution reported to the BIPM was estimated by the TDCR method (A_{RCTD1}) at the reference date of August 23, 2024 12 h UTC. In the SIR procedure for short-lived radionuclides, at least two measurements are performed. The comparison result obtained using the first SIR measurement using a half-life of 10.64 (1) h (Bé et al., 2004) yields an equivalent activity of 12 070 (40) kBq, with a relative uncertainty of 0.33 % obtained by combining the uncertainty of the TDCR activity standardization and the uncertainty of the SIR measurement of 0.10 %. The second SIR measurement provides a result in agreement within 0.03 %.

Because the present ^{212}Pb submission was the first participation in the SIR for this radionuclide, no key comparison reference value and degree of equivalence could be evaluated. However, the photon and electron response curves of the SIR ionization chamber versus energy evaluated using the SIRIC software are well established (Cox et al., 2007) and enable the equivalent activity for any photon-emitting radionuclide to be calculated, using known photon and electron emission intensities. In the particular case of ^{212}Pb , the ^{212}Bi and ^{208}Tl progeny must be taken into account using the related equilibrium coefficients. The ^{212}Pb equivalent activity at equilibrium calculated using SIRIC software was equal to 12 040 (160) kBq, with a relative uncertainty of 1.3 %, which mainly comes from the decay data of ^{212}Pb and its progeny (DDEP recommended data, 2024). With a difference of 0.25 %, the SIRIC software value agrees within standard uncertainty with the LNE-LNHB BIPM.RI(II)-K1 comparison result, which is an indication of the reliability of decay data and the primary standard.

7. Summary and discussion

A primary standard of ^{212}Pb in equilibrium with its progeny based on the TDCR method was developed at LNHB using a radioactive solution of ^{212}Pb -DOTAMTATE supplied by Orano Med (France). Additional activity concentration measurements were carried out by $4\pi(\text{LS})\beta$ - γ and $4\pi\gamma$ counting leading to consistent values within their related uncertainties.

Table 12

Comparison between the most important absolute γ -photon intensities of ^{212}Pb , ^{212}Bi and ^{208}Tl obtained in this work with recently published measurements from NIST and NPL (Pibida et al., 2024) and DDEP recommended data.

Energy /keV	Parent radionuclide	NIST (2024)	NPL (2024)	DDEP	This work
115.18	^{212}Pb	0.00593 (4)	0.005734 (51)	0.00624 (23)	0.00568 (12)
238.63	^{212}Pb	0.4316 (24)	0.4321 (34)	0.436 (5)	0.4315 (33)
277.37	^{208}Tl	0.06336 (29)	0.06430 (53)	0.066 (3)	0.0639 (10)
300.09	^{212}Pb	0.03202 (18)	0.03260 (26)	0.0318 (14)	0.03258 (47)
583.19	^{208}Tl	0.83475 (443)	0.8431 (66)	0.850 (3)	0.837 (7)
727.33	^{212}Bi	0.06520 (35)	0.06545 (53)	0.0665 (4)	0.0659 (10)
763.45	^{208}Tl	0.01765 (14)	0.01763 (24)	0.0180 (2)	0.0171 (8)
785.37	^{212}Bi	0.01076 (7)	0.01083 (11)	0.0111 (1)	0.01039 (35)
860.53	^{208}Tl	0.1237 (6)	0.1244 (10)	0.124 (1)	0.1222 (22)

TDCR counting using the Hidex 300 SL apparatus at LNHB also yields activity results in good agreement. Further investigations will be needed to explain the discrepancies observed in the case of α -counting by the DSA method.

The primary standard was transferred to the Vinten 671 IC for the BIPM and LMRI types of ampoules. Comparison between experimental and calculated calibration coefficients based on the Penelope and Geant4 MC codes yields satisfactory results. As reported in Bergeron et al. (2002b), the IC response for ^{212}Pb in equilibrium with its progeny is predominantly due to the contribution of ^{208}Tl day (about 80 %). A specific ampoule was submitted for BIPM-SIR measurements. The equivalent activity obtained with the SIRIC software is in good agreement within standard uncertainty with the LNE-LNHB BIPM.RI(II)-K1 comparison result. Thus, the comparisons with simulated calibration coefficients and with the calculated equivalent activity for the SIR measurements can be both interpreted as good indicators of the reliability of the primary standard of ^{212}Pb at LNHB. The radioactive decay measurements with a Centronic IG11 IC gave a half-life equal to 10.6314 (74) h, which is slightly lower than the DDEP recommended value (10.64 (1) h (Bé et al., 2004)) as for the most recent published values (Kossert, 2017; Bergmann and Jelínek, 2022; Pibida et al., 2024). The absolute γ -photon emissions measured in this work are also consistent with the recent comprehensive study published in Pibida et al. (2024).

CRediT authorship contribution statement

C. Bobin: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **M.-N. Amiot:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Project administration, Validation, Writing – original draft. **C. Michotte:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Software, Validation, Writing – original draft. **B. Boyer:** Formal analysis, Investigation, Software, Validation, Writing – original draft. **C. Carceller:** Formal analysis, Validation. **L. Chambon:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Validation, Writing – original draft, Methodology. **R. Coulon:** Software, Validation. **S. Courte:** Validation. **C. Dulieu:** Formal analysis, Validation. **M. Loidl:** Formal analysis, Validation. **V. Lourenço:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **S. Morrelli:** Formal analysis, Validation. **S. Pierre:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Methodology, Software, Validation, Writing – original draft. **B. Sabot:** Software. **C. Thiam:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Writing – original draft.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This work was performed using a radioactive solution of ^{212}Pb -DOTAMTATE supplied by Orano Med (France). This study was supported by the project (22HLT03 AlphaMet), which has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology (EPM), co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the participating States.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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